

The contribution of formal and non-formal training programs in Vietnam's manufacturing sector

Skills for Industry Policy Brief Vietnam #3 (2024)

At a glance:

This policy brief examines the contribution of formal and non-formal training programs in Vietnam's manufacturing sector in terms of meeting skills needs of manufacturing industries, productivity, transformation, and growth. The findings indicated that:

- 1.1 Non-formal training programs are recognized for their perceived efficacy in addressing current industry-specific skill gaps but also ensuring future competitiveness in a sector that is constantly evolving.
- 1.2 Conversely, formal training programs, while also viewed positively, garner less enthusiasm, particularly for lower-level positions.
- 1.3 The underdevelopment of the formal TVET system necessitates a shift towards non-formal and informal training, often provided by technology-transferring entities, creating a competitive advantage over traditional TVET providers.

Introduction:

Vietnam's economic landscape has undergone a remarkable transformation since the initiation of economic reforms in 1986. By opening its doors to the world, the nation has experienced a surge in growth, with the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) expanding over ten times from 26 billion USD in 1986 to 409 billion USD by 2022 (World Bank, 2024). This achievement has propelled Vietnam from the status of a poor country to that of a lower-middle-income country.

Several studies (Glewwe et al. 2004; Stefan 2017; Van Dinh 2018; and Baum 2020), have explored the factors contributing to Vietnam's economic success. These studies aim to analyze the complexities of this growth trajectory, offering insights into the policies, strategies, and initiatives that have shaped the nation's economy.

In this context, the third policy brief of the Skills for Industry project seeks to address a critical question: what contributions do formal and non-formal training programs make in alleviating skills shortages, driving transformative changes, and fostering sustained growth within Vietnam's manufacturing industries?

To answer this question, our research methodology involved the collection of comprehensive data through a survey of 162 manufacturing companies in the garment, electronics, and food processing

industries, and subsequent encoding and analysis using descriptive statistical methods. Additionally, interview memos were translated from Vietnamese to English, making the insights more accessible to a broader audience. A thematic analysis was employed to derive meaningful patterns and trends from the qualitative data, thus providing a nuanced understanding of the contributions made by formal and non-formal training programs.

The findings presented herein aim to inform policymakers, industry leaders, and educators, and offer actionable recommendations to further fortify the nation’s position on the global economic stage.

Insights:

1. Contribution to meeting skills needs

Figure 1 illustrates the significant role played by both pre-employment and in-employment training programs in meeting the skill requirements of the three manufacturing industries being surveyed. Feedback from manufacturing company managers shows that these training initiatives have made noteworthy contributions. Nearly all managers across the three sectors unanimously agreed that both pre-employment and in-employment TVET programs contribute to meet their industry’s skill requirements, categorizing their impact as either “significant” or “somewhat”.

Interestingly, a closer look at the differences between the two types of training programs shows that in-employment training is consistently rated higher than pre-employment training. This discrepancy is especially pronounced in the garment industry, with 71% of managers highlighting the significant role of in-employment training, as opposed to 12% for pre-employment training. However, the gap is smaller in the electronics sector, where 44% of managers value in-employment training highly, versus 14% for pre-employment training.

Figure 1: Contribution of formal and non-formal TVET programs to meeting skills needs of manufacturing industries.

Note: Response to the question “Please assess if the programmes catering to your employees ... have contributed to meeting your skills needs”. Pre: Pre-employment / In: In-employment. Information from 162 companies.

Figure 2 further illustrates the impact of pre- and in-employment training programs across different occupational levels. There is a consensus on their contribution across all occupational levels. However, pre-employment training receives distinctly lower ratings than in-employment training, although there is a discernible upward trend in ratings from general worker roles to managerial positions for both types. It is intriguing that pre-employment and in-employment training programs are not seen as interchangeable, but instead appear to complement each other, with their usage rising concurrently across hierarchical occupation levels. An exception is found with general workers, where no utilization of pre-employment programs was recorded.

Figure 2: Contribution of formal and non-formal TVET programs to meeting skills needs at the occupational levels.

Note: Response to the question “Please assess if the programmes catering to your employees ... have contributed to meeting your skills needs”. Pre: Pre-employment / In: In-employment. Information from 162 companies.

2. Contribution to productivity

In interviews with 36 representatives from 18 manufacturing firms, including human resources and production managers, it was evident that companies perceive employees with formal TVET qualifications to outperform those without such formal training. This is true for a number of dimensions, including a reduced need for supervision, enhanced problem-solving capabilities, quicker and more precise task execution, and fewer errors.

Figure 3 summarizes the responses. A notable 86% of company and production managers either strongly agree or agree that individuals with TVET qualifications necessitate less oversight than those without formal training. In terms of problem-solving, all respondents signalled their strong agreement or agreement, associating this skill with employees holding TVET qualifications. Similarly, 94% of managers concurred that such employees work faster and with more precision. Regarding error minimization, 86% of the respondents acknowledged a connection with formal TVET training.

Figure 3: The contribution of formal TVET programs to productivity.

Note: Based on the responses from 18 companies (36 company and production managers).

3. Contribution to transformation and growth

The transformation in manufacturing is driven by three key factors: “making easier to introduce new product”, “adapting faster to new technology”, and “adapting faster to change in work organization”. Figure 4 shows the impact of employees with formal TVET qualifications on these areas, as well as on the overall growth of manufacturing companies. A substantial 98% of respondents strongly agree or agree that employees with formal TVET qualifications streamline the introduction of new products, bolstering innovation and new product development in manufacturing sectors. Similarly, the same percentage of respondents recognize these employees’ ability to quickly adapt to new technology and organizational changes. This showcases their agility in embracing technological advancements and evolving work setups. Notably, all managers acknowledged that employees with TVET qualifications are “an important factor for growth”. This highlights the pivotal role of TVET in driving the growth and expansion of manufacturing industries.

Figure 4: The contribution of formal TVET to transformation and growth.

Note: Based on the responses from 18 companies (36 company and production managers).

Conclusion:

In summary, both pre-employment training, in the form of formal qualifications, and in-employment training, which includes non-formal and informal

training methods, are essential for addressing the skill requirements of the manufacturing sector. Notably, in-employment training is often viewed as more influential due to its practical nature.

Training initiatives positively influence all occupational levels, yet the significance of pre-employment and ongoing non-formal and informal training increases in more advanced job roles. It is crucial to recognize that while pre-employment and in-employment training programs serve distinct purposes, their integration is vital for comprehensive skill development throughout the workforce. This combined approach is key to tailoring training efforts to meet the varied needs of the industry, from entry-level positions to top management.

Further examination reveals that employees holding formal TVET qualifications are often perceived as more productive. They generally require less supervision, commit fewer errors, and carry out tasks with greater speed and precision. This efficiency underscores the direct impact of TVET qualifications on productivity within manufacturing environments.

Together, these findings emphasize the need for a robust and adaptive training system that not only meets current industry demands but also prepares the workforce for future challenges, thereby securing a competitive edge in the global market.

Recommendations to policy makers:

- Recognize the effectiveness of non-formal training in addressing industry-specific skill gaps unaddressed by formal TVET programs. Advocate and support for companies to invest and diversify in-employment training opportunities to boost employees' performance and drive overall organizational efficiency and adaptability.
- Assess and overhaul formal TVET programs, incorporating successful elements of non-formal

training, ensuring enhanced relevance and quality. Foster partnerships with technology-transferring entities, recognizing their potential to provide a competitive advantage.

- Advocate for a better integration of formal and non-formal programs and training models to leverage the advantage of both models, and effectively and efficiently prepare for evolving industry demands.

By implementing these recommendations, Vietnam's manufacturing sector can build a more adaptable, skilled, and competitive workforce, ready to meet the challenges of a rapidly evolving industry landscape.

References:

- Baun, A. (2019). Vietnam's Development Success Story and the Unfinished. Retrieved from www.imf.org/Files/English/wp/iea2020031-print.pdf
- Chryssolouris, G., Mavrikios, D. & Mourtzis, D. (2013). Manufacturing Systems: Skills & Competencies for the Future. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/257745808_Manufacturing_Systems_Skills_Competencies_for_the_Future
- Glewwe, P., Nisha Agrawal, N. & Dollar, C. (2004). Economic Growth, Poverty, and Household Welfare in Vietnam. Retrieved from <http://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/492311468317977923/pdf/290860rev.pdf>
- Stefan, T. (2017). Education in Vietnam. <https://wenr.wes.org/2017/11/education-in-vietnam>
- Van Dinh (2018). The Future of ASEAN: Viet Nam Perspective. Retrieved from <https://www.pwc.com/vn/en/publications/2018/future-of-asean-vietnam-perspective.pdf>

- WorldBank(2024).GDP(currentUS\$)-Vietnam.
Retrieved from <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.CD?locations=VN>
- World Bank (2021). Skills development.
Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/skillsdevelopment>

Author: Vi Hoang Dang, Thuy Thanh Nguyen, Luyen Huu Nguyen, Vinh Ngoc Hoang

Editor: Andrea Kreuzer

Contact: dhvi70@gmail.com,
andrea.kreuzer@phzh.ch

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